

A Pictorial Map in the Dongdasi: A Chinese Cosmological Representation of Islamic Pilgrimage Sites

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In the prayer hall of the Dongdasi - the Great East Mosque - in Xian hangs a unique map showing the Holy Sites of Arabia painted on a large wood panel (Fig. 1). Rendered in tempera in clear bright colours, the map depicts nearly all of the holy places in and around Mecca (Makka) and Medina (Madina). These sites are recognisable because they are similar to topographical images found in Ottoman pilgrimage books dating from the late-17th and early-18th centuries. By comparing the painting with illustrations in these manuscripts, I believe that it was created in China sometime after 1700 and - based on the style of its borders - before 1850.

The arrangement of sites on the map, although highly structured, is geographically unrealistic and does not conform to the customary order of visitation. Yet, the formal composition suggests that the pattern made sense to the Chinese artist. Curious as to the meaning of this novel arrangement, I photographed the panel, studied it, and eventually developed a theory about its composition based on principles found in Chinese cosmology.

When I first visited the mosque in 1981, a helpful mosque attendant noticed my interest in the map and explained that it was used to teach students the significance of these ancient pietistic sites. Twenty-two in number, these include the pilgrimage sites of the *hajj*¹ as well as the *ziyara*, post-Islamic "stations" of visitation. Meticulously detailed, the map is clearly an ideal teaching tool. It is a tribute to the artist that these diagrammatic illustrations still serve as potent didactic symbols, and have endured the test of time.²

A unique blending of Western Islamic and Chinese tradition, the map is in keeping with the ethnic diversity of the Dongdasi's congregation, which traces its roots to the 8th century - when Arab and Persian merchants first arrived in Xian (formerly Chang'an), the Tang capital on the old Silk Route. They were later followed by Turkish traders, who settled in large numbers in this area of northwestern China. Built largely in the early 15th century in the style of an early Ming dynasty Buddhist temple, the Dongdasi³ is the largest mosque of the dozen or so that were built in Xian. Like the map discussed in this article, the artefacts and architecture of the Dongdasi are an enduring expression of cross-cultural exchange, and the increasing presence of Muslims in China, who today number around 55 million.

General Description

On entering the mosque, I noticed two panels of pilgrimage sites, separated by a doorway, that hung on the rear (west) wall which parishioners face when praying (the mosque is at the right in Fig. 2). The map to the right of the door was brown and faded, most

likely water stained. It was in such poor condition that I could not see how it related to the other panel, which, despite some paint deterioration was in relatively good condition. The colours of this one - red, green, and grey on a creamy white background are clear and vivid. Gold was used sparingly - for small details and the embellishment of the richly painted borders. Some of the paint, especially of the background, has flaked away. This can be explained by seasonal changes in temperature and humidity, and the panel itself having absorbed moisture.⁴ Set in a green wooden frame, the map measures approximately 213 x 105 cm.⁵ There is an additional 10 cm border with a meandering chrysanthemum scroll surrounding the whole, and at the base are other borders measuring about 26 cm in total, decorated with other floral and Chinese design motifs.

The individual sites, arranged in a grid-like pattern are organised into three distinct vertical columns, in a manner that parallels the planning of Chinese imperial cities. The wide middle column, on a north-south axis, contains the most important sites with the Holy Mosque at Mecca in the centre (Fig. 1-B), the Holy Mount of Jabal al-Rahman at Arafat at the top (Fig. 1-K), and the Prophet's Mosque in Medina at the bottom (Fig. 1-R). The remaining sites are arranged in two flanking columns.

The only feature of the map not found in traditional Islamic sites, is a triple gateway (Fig. 1-A) inserted in the upper right hand corner. Three banners fly aloft and oil lamps are suspended from each of the arches. A tripartite gateway or *pailou* of Buddhist and Confucian temples was familiar to a local Muslim congregation, and one had been used as an honorary entranceway to the Dongdasi, which as noted, was designed in the style of a Buddhist temple. Such a gateway can be seen at the left of the Dongdasi (see Fig. 2). The one depicted on the panel may well have been intended to mark the holy ground just outside of Mecca, where pilgrims commence the *hajj*.

Banners are used sparingly on the map, and apparently celebrate the particular sanctity of a location, as found on this archway. Their appearance on the panel is limited to Jabal al-Rahman (Fig. 1-K) in the plain of Arafat, next to the hills marking the entrance to Mina (Fig. 1-N); and at Muzdalifa (Fig. 1-M), suggesting that Chinese Muslims took a strict legalistic view of pilgrimage by singling out - besides the Ka'ba - the three most important stations of visitation on a *hajj*.

Ottoman Pilgrimage Guides

The fine detailing and complexity of the shrines on the Chinese map suggests a meticulously rendered prototype. A com-

Fig. 1. Pictorial Map of the Holy Sites of Arabia in the Dongdasi.

Key to Holy Sites:

- A Gateway outside of Mecca
- B The Holy Mosque of Mecca
- C Safa
- D Marwa
- E Jabal Abu Qubbays
- F Souk al-Layl
- G Cemetery at Ma'la
- H Town of Mu'da
- I Jabal Nur
- J Jabal Thawr
- K Jabal al-Rahman at Arafat
- L Namira Mosque at Arafat
- M Muzdalifa
- N Valley of Mina
- O Mosque of Khayf
- P Jabal Mifra
- Q Mosque of Ali
- R Mosque of the Prophet at Medina
- S Mosque of Quba
- T Shrines at Medina
- U Uhud
- V Mosque of Hamza

parison of the panel with illustrations in particular Ottoman manuscripts containing a pilgrimage guide - the *Binney Anthology* in the Arthur M. Sackler Museum at Harvard University Art Museums⁶ and the *Futuh al-Haramayn* (The Conquest of the Two Holy Sites) by Muhyi Lari in the British Library Or. 343,⁷ reveal some striking similarities and indicate that the artist at Xian used a similar book as guide to his painting.

These and other pilgrimage books, with their devotional text, small portable size (on average about 22 x 15 cm), and non-imperial style of illustration would have made ideal keepsakes of the sacred journey to Mecca. Under *Pax Mongolia*, Chinese Muslims were making the *hajj* from at least as early as the Yuan period (1260-1368). One or more of these Ottoman books must have reached China during the high Qing period (1644-1912), carried by a pilgrim or

Fig. 2. Scroll painting with view of the Dongdasi

merchant returning from Arabia. Evidence for the travel that existed between Central Asia and Mecca may be found in the colophon at the first section of the *Binney Anthology* (fol. 68r), which is signed, "Muhammad ibn Yar Muhammad from Balkh" - Balkh being a city on the route to Xian.

The *Futub al-Haramayn*, the *Binney Anthology*, and other pilgrimage books are devoted largely to appropriate prayers and wandering poetic descriptions of the sacred sites and rituals. Not surprisingly, the pilgrimage guides do not constitute a cohesive school of painting. Their illustrations, generally prosaic in character, suggest that they were not the *raison d'être* of manuscript production but were included primarily as mementos. While some appear to have been done by skilled artists, most appear to be the work of local artists in the bazaars at Mecca. The interest in architectural representation found in these guides may reflect a pride in the active program of renovation and reconstruction that occurred when the sites were under Ottoman sovereignty. Each site described in these books would merit its own illustration on a separate folio, with each component clearly labelled. Two or more holy sites were depicted together horizontally in the format of a pilgrimage scroll from the 13th century on,⁸ which encouraged a "film strip" approach. The sites also appear together in a more abbreviated, vertical format on Ottoman tiles.⁹

Despite their popularity and the fact that almost every Muslim country has produced a wide array of pilgrimage literature over the centuries, very little is known about the transmission of texts, with or without illustrations, and the specific meaning and history of pilgrimage literature. Clearly, these books were not meant to function as travel guides or *Baedekers* for the Holy Sites. Pilgrims of the times of these manuscripts relied on a professional guide (*dalil* or *mutawwif*) to lead them through the rites and rituals, just as today's pilgrims do.

Pilgrimage Guides as Points of Comparison

The Dongdasi map relies on a conventionalised style of architectural representation comparable to manuscript illustration in Ottoman pilgrimage guides, and does not include details that might be attributed to personal observation. The portrayal of shrines is diagrammatic and symbolic, freely combining plans of arcaded courtyards and elevations to display important exterior and interior details. Ottoman artists of the mid-16th century already showed a facility with this method of illustration, as seen in the earliest copy of the *Futub al-Haramayn* (Istanbul, Topkapı Palace Library, R.917).¹⁰ This pre-perspectival manner of depiction and

the rendering of particular historical details helps to date and identify the *Binney Anthology* and the *Futub al-Haramayn* in the British Library as the type of manuscript the Xian artist might have used. The lack of European perspective indicates that these books must date before the middle of the 18th century.

Of the two pilgrimage guides cited, the *Anthology* illustrations are the most complete and finely illuminated with gold details - suitable for the taste of a rich merchant. In its depictions of the sanctuaries at Mecca and Medina and the important sites of Arafat and Mina it offers the most reliable source of comparison with the Chinese map. The colophon of the first section of the *Anthology* (fol. 68r) provides Mecca as its provenance, stating "written at Mecca the Blessed in 990/1582". (The date is obviously spurious since the illustration includes the seventh minaret at the Holy Mosque.) The *Futub al-Haramayn* is highly detailed but its illustrations lack rich illumination - in keeping with a client of more modest means. The manuscript is probably a little later in date than the *Anthology* as indicated by such details as the inclusion of the domed entranceways in the Prophet's Mosque in Medina. Most detail found in the Chinese map also appears in one or both of these two works. The artist made no attempt to record changes at these sites. With the exception of the depiction of hills and mountains, there is no evidence that the artist infused a Chinese sense of aesthetics in the portrayal of any particular site.

The careful attention to detail in the panel suggests that a skilled professional artist carefully studied each monument in its original format as a book illustration. Images on the map are generally twice as large as corresponding pictures in, for example, the *Binney Anthology*, which measure approximately 22.2 x 14.5 cm.¹¹ Given the Chinese reverence for mountains and their cosmological significance, the representation of hills and mountains on the map are strikingly monumental, at least two thirds the size of those in the *Anthology*. It would seem that the artist achieved his fine detail more easily by doubling the original architectural representations, especially the rendering of the Holy Mosque at Mecca and the Prophet's Mosque at Medina.

The depiction of the most important sanctuary at Mecca is strikingly similar to those found in scenes of Ottoman pilgrimage guides from the 17th century on. The site is always shown in the most conventional manner with important historical detail. The Dongdasi map and the *Binney Anthology* and the *Futub al-Haramayn* in particular share stylistic similarities and details - number of arcades and style and placement of Ottoman minarets with two balconies - including the seventh minaret, added between 1603-17 by Sultan Ahmed. The inclusion of the 17th minaret provides the earliest date possible for these illustrations.

Fig. 3. Holy Mosque at Mecca in the Edwin Binney 3rd *Anthology*, fol. 36v in the Arthur M. Sackler Museum at Harvard University Art Museums, Cambridge, MA. 1985.265.

Description of Individual Pilgrimage Sites

The sites on the panel are described below in the order found in a typical 17th century pilgrimage guide.

The Holy Mosque of Mecca¹² (Masjid al-Haram; Fig. 1-B) with the Ka'ba - a small cubicle building enclosing the Black Stone, and said to have been built by Abraham - commands the centre of the panel. This is fitting since the Ka'ba is indeed the spiritual centre of Islam. Pilgrims always begin their journey with a sevenfold circumambulation of the Ka'ba, touching its corners, and kissing the Black Stone. Religious convention directs that the door of the Ka'ba be prominently displayed in frontal view with the revered Black Stone placed at the lower left. The entrance into the *matraf*, the pavement on which the rites of circumambulation are performed, is also turned to the front so that the *hijr*, the semicircular wall associated with Ismael, is seen at the right, although the paint has deteriorated here. The long walls of the sanctuary have been shifted to a south-north orientation, rather than a realistic northwest-southeast alignment. Both this mosque and the Prophet's Mosque in Medina are depicted in accord with Islamic cartographic tradition which orients south at the top and north below.

As in the *Binney Anthology*, fol. 36v, (Fig. 3) and the *Futub al-Haramayn*, fol. 17v, the Holy Mosque has a large open *sabn* (courtyard) surrounded on all four sides by a domed, double arcade.¹³ Arches in the inner arcade are rounded, while in the outer arcade

they are tri-lobed, alternating with undecorated stonework. Honorific oil lamps hang from each of the arches. The panel also shares with these manuscript illustrations a number of other features: the placement of the seven minarets with three at the bottom of the courtyard - red, green and red as in the Binney version - and two on the exterior at the right and two on the exterior at the corners, each with two Ottoman-style balconies. There is also a domed entrance in the middle of the arcade at the top and a diagonal orientation for the corner arches, as well as the schematic depiction of buildings surrounding the Ka'ba. Datable features include the addition of the seventh minaret to the mosque, built between 1603-17, and the restoration of the *riwaqs* (arcades), which were fitted with domes after 1557 and reconstructed between 1572-77.

The buildings inside the *matraf* at the north are shown from the front, and include the double red and green storied Zamzam (well house), at the left, the domed Maqam Ibrahim next to it, which protects the stone bearing Abraham's footprints, the *mimbar* (pulpit), used for sermons, at the right, and the staircase used for entering the Ka'ba.

Outside the *matraf*, the buildings which encircle the Ka'ba include the Maqam Hanafi (a double-storied structure) at the right, the Maqam Maliki at the top, and the Maqam Hanbali, all with Ottoman gabled roofs, where the Imams of these three schools of religious law pray. The Zamzam was used by the Imam of the fourth school of law, the Shafi'is. The two other structures at the outer edge of the *sabn* are a building used for housing the implements of the mosque and a domed water tank.

In this version of the Holy Mosque, the paved *matraf*, exterior brick or tile work, floral bands encircling the domes, and decorative details in gold found in the *Binney Anthology* scene are not depicted. Such features would have been alien to a Chinese artist, whose decorative training is expressed in the borders along the bottom of the map.

In the upper left portion of the panel, the *via sacra* begins with Safa (Fig. 1-C) with its three arched gateway and ends with Marwa (Fig. 1-D), a long arcaded court where pilgrims perform the *sa'y*, a running back and forth seven times in memory of Hagar's search for water. The gate is raised on steps with lamps hanging from the arches and stands next to a well. Nearby is a tree, probably the thornless lote-tree, a symbol of heavenly bliss mentioned in the Qur'an.¹⁴ The court terminates in a wide semicircular apse with two pairs of green piers, religious markers. Honorific lamps are suspended from each of the arches.

The holy mount, Jabal Abu Qubbays (Fig. 1-E), is depicted towering over Safa and Marwa, as in fact it does, but here it is shown in the northwest, not the east. A red gateway to the mountainous hill is shown at its base. This mount is especially important because it is believed that the Black Stone was buried there during Noah's flood. It is also thought to be the burial place of Adam. The Chinese reverence for nature finds expression in the depiction of the mountain as verdant and green rather than the mauve or blue tints found in most manuscript illustrations, which may suggest its desert surroundings. This is also the mountain where the moon, according to Muslim tradition split in half when the Prophet stood at the mountain's apex.

To the left of Marwa is the Souk al-Layl (Fig. 1-F), with domed shrines honouring the birthplaces of the Prophet, his wife, Khadija, Ali, his cousin and son-in-law, and Abu Bakr, his successor. The Prophet's daughter Fatima and her two sons, Hasan and Husayn, were also born there.

The sacred cemetery of Mecca, Ma'la (Fig. 1-G), with the tombs of Amina, the Prophet's mother, and other members of his family, is shown directly below the souk. It is represented schematically with

Fig. 4. Jabal al-Rahman and the valley of Arafat, Binney *Anthology*, 53r, 1985.265.

for many hours. As in the Binney *Anthology*, fol. 53r (Fig. 4), banners wave at the hillside, and a domed shrine, Umin Salama, caps the top. Shown here are two gold-coloured gilded brass Ottoman *chiragban* - oil burning candelabra on long poles used for extensive night illumination during religious and secular celebrations. The enormous width of the mountain helps to emphasise its religious importance. According to the observant 19th-century English traveller, Richard Burton, the Mount of Mercy is actually a "mass of course granite split into large blocks, with a thin coat of withered thorns. About one mile in circumference, it rises abruptly to the height of 180 feet, from the low gravelly plain".¹⁵ Tents for shade are pitched at the base of the mountain, and nearby, the arcaded Namira mosque (Fig. 1-L), with two doorways, is shown facing the Ka'ba. Next to it are three large tents (*mabamil*) that were carried by camels as symbols of wealth and power.

Placed at the lower left corner of the Holy Mosque at Mecca is Muzdalifa (Fig. 1-M), where pilgrims spend the night when returning from Arafat. It is the second most important place for worship, ritual prayer, and delivery of sermon during the *hajj*. The site has a building with a stepped-roof (a mosque?), next to a mound - probably the holy hill of Kuzah - and a smaller structure whose roof appears damaged due to paint flaking. The two buildings are on a raised platform with small banners to mark the importance of the site. There are two large *chiragban* below.

The valley of Mina (Fig. 1-N), the third site for visitation on a *hajj*, stretches to the right of the Ka'ba. At Mina, pilgrims spend three days praying, stoning the devil, and sacrificing animals. Its placement opposite Muzdalifa serves to balance the composition, but in reality, the two sites are due east of Mecca, and in close proximity. As found in the depiction of Mina in the *Anthology*, fol. 57r (Fig. 5), there are two hills at the entrance of Mina (a large banner calls additional attention to this), tents that lie in front and behind the arcaded streets, and the Jamrat al-Akahab, a stone pillar in front of a hill, where the Devil is stoned seven times by each

two small, domed shrines and four rectangular graves.

The town of Mud'a (Fig. 1-H), with its double-arcaded street market, lies directly below Marwa. Each arcaded street has six arches with suspended oil lamps, and a green pier marking its religious importance. Clearly, the Chinese artist was not familiar with an Arabian souk because the two streets are widely separated.

Jabal Nur (the holy Mount of Light also called Jabal Hira, Fig. 1-I), directly below the Holy Mosque of Mecca at the right, is where the Prophet received his first revelation in the Cave of Hira (not the white circular spot) and spent a month each year. At its summit is a small, domed red building with a lamp hanging from its entrance. This rocky mountain is traditionally coloured gold, because of the golden sand that is said to be at its summit. Instead, the Chinese artist coloured it green, and realistically depicted its shape - a steeply sloping mass, topped by a rocky mound. He also attempted to make the mountain appear more three-dimensional than is typical in most guides, using short striations for texturing, and a valley its base.

To the left of Jabal Nur is the holy mount of Jabal Thawr (Bull Mountain, Fig. 1-J), where the Prophet hid from the hostile Quraysh tribe in a cave, also outlined in red. It is somewhat naturalistically depicted, like a pyramid with stepped sides. Paint deterioration explains the white area in it at the left.

Jabal al-Rahman, the holy Mount of Mercy (Fig. 1-K), in the valley of Arafat, occupies the honoured position at the top of the map, on axis with the Ka'ba and the Prophet's Mosque at Medina. Jabal al-Rahman is where the central ceremonies of the *hajj* take place, including the main sermon of the *hajj*, in memory of one that Muhammad preached. It is here that, standing in adoration and asking forgiveness, pilgrims fervently recite ritual prayers together

Fig. 5. Valley of Mina with the Mosque of Khayf, Binney *Anthology*, 57r, 1985.265.

pilgrim. Between the streets, are two additional stone pillars. Also in the valley of Mina, below the tents at the left, is the Mosque of Khayf (Fig. 1-O), which commemorates a place where Muhammad once pitched his tent. It has a tall minaret behind the entrance, and a small domed building in the courtyard with a four-arched arcade on only one side. The rocky mount of Marsalat, facing left, adjacent to the mosque and a *chiragban* below, are also depicted.

Jabal Mifra (Mount of Good Cheer, Fig. 1-P), is the granite hill at the right of the picture, directly below the Mosque of Khayf. Under the hill, in an oasis of palm trees near Medina, is the Mosque of the martyr Ali (Fig. 1-Q), a rectangular mosque shown in outline only, with a whitewashed facade surmounted by a vaulted roof.

The Mosque of the Prophet (Fig. 1-R), which most pilgrims use the occasion of the *hajj* to visit, is on axis with Mecca and Arafat and dominates the lower half of the painting. It is shown according to Ottoman pre-perspectival tradition, and such basic architectural features as the multiple aisles of the prayer hall and of the arcades, which open on the interior courtyard, are omitted. Instead, the map shares with other imaginative depictions of Medina (e.g., Binney *Anthology*, fol. 63r; see Fig. 6), certain specific iconographic motifs. These include use of a rectangular plan showing a continuous, single-aisled, arcaded wall surmounted by alternating red and green crests or domes (or a combination of both). (The latter are difficult to see on the panel due to paint damage.) The arcades open onto the interior courtyard with Fatima's garden and surround the small prayer hall with the Noble Dome over the Prophet's tomb. Due to paint damage, the tombs of the Prophet and of Fatima are not clear on the panel. Only a fragment of the Noble Dome can be seen at the left, and it is green, not blue, as in the *Anthology* scene. In the year 1253/1837, the blue dome was, in fact, replaced by a green one. However, given that blue was not used on the panel in the depiction of architecture or landscape, the attempt at verisimilitude is questionable.

Several readily identifiable features help to date the Chinese painting. As in the *Anthology* version, two minarets are placed in the interior corners of the courtyard, another at the right, parallel to the outside wall, and two more at the exterior corners flanking the Noble Dome. The fifth minaret at the left, barely visible due to paint damage, was rebuilt after 990/1582. The domed cubical treasury of the Prophet in the courtyard was rebuilt at the direction of Sultan Suleyman in 974/1566 for storing oil and candles. The four doorways (perhaps with domes?) on the eastern and western sides of the courtyard (those at the left are especially hard to see, again due to paint damage), and the four arcades (*riwaqs*) opening on to the courtyard can be attributed to the reconstruction by the Mamluk Sultan Qa'it Bey in 888/1483. The other datable features are the two parallel *mibrabs* ordered by Sultan Suleyman and the part-coloured *mimbar* (pulpit) in the prayer hall, made at the direction of Sultan Murad III in 998/1589. The mosque acquired some of its domes under Sultan Murad IV in 1044/1634 and by 1729 had domed arcades on all four sides.¹⁶ If some of the arcades on the Dongdasi painting are indeed domed - not just stepped - this would help in dating its prototype.

The Mosque of Quba (Fig. 1-S), above the Mosque of the Prophet at the left, with a foundation laid by the Prophet when he came to Medina, has a white washed facade, and an Ottoman style minaret attached to a rectangular building, with a five-arched balcony surmounted by a stepped roof.

The four small shrines (Fig. 1-T), in the left corner of the painting, are traditionally those of the Prophet, Ali, Uthman, and Abu Bakr. The structure with two arches surmounted by a dome is probably meant to be a small building with a double *mibrab*. Palm trees and water wells evoke the oasis setting of Medina.

Fig. 6. Mosque of the Prophet at Medina, Binney *Anthology*, 63r, 1985.265.

In the opposite corner, at the right, is the final site included in the map, the Mosque of Hamza (Fig. 1-V) and the mountain of Uhud (Fig. 1-U), which Richard Burton described as "rising like a mass of iron". There Muhammad lost an important battle. The cave where the Prophet took refuge during the battle is at the right, adjacent to the large boulder on which he leaned while going to Uhud. The mountain is a popular religious site which he visited every year. Nearby is the Mosque of Hamza (Fig. 1-V), the "Lord of Martyrs" and uncle of the Prophet, who migrated to Medina with him and was killed at the Battle of Uhud. The mosque is built over Hamza's tomb.

Chinese Principles of Organisation

While the individual depiction of the Holy Sites follows Ottoman tradition, combining all 22 sites in a single, rectangular composition is unprecedented and innovative. This would have presented a unique challenge to the Chinese artist. On what basis did the Chinese artist decide to organise the painting?

The answer appears to lie in the cosmological principles used to structure Chinese imperial cities from ancient times on. These cities were always carefully laid out in the belief that it was essential to harmonise with natural phenomena - mountains, wind, water (*fengshui*).

Of prime importance was the alignment of the Imperial Palace on the main central axis, which faced south and was often bordered at the north by a protective mountain or hill (sometimes, even an artificial one) and by water at the south. Both the Imperial Palace

Fig. 7. Cosmological Mandala of the Yuan dynasty (1279-1368) in the Metropolitan Museum of Art, New York, 1989.140.

and the Hall of Audience in front of it were bordered by an Ancestral Temple on the east and lesser altars on the west. The whole city formed a square, with streets and markets laid out in a grid pattern.¹⁷

The Dongdasi painting is organised, roughly, into three vertical columns, mirroring the city plan of Xian (Chang'an) during the Tang dynasty.¹⁸ The artist positioned the three most significant sites, the Jabal al-Rahman at Arafat, the Ka'ba at Mecca, and the sanctuary at Medina, in the centre column. Here, Jabal al-Rahman at Arafat, protects the Ka'ba at the north - in reality it is to the east of Mecca. The placement of both Jabal Nur and Jabal Thawr to the south of the Ka'ba and next to one another, is also geographically unrealistic. These lush green mountains may be meant to stand symbolically for water, which as noted above, is usually placed to the south.

The two flanking columns contain the other pilgrimage sites. The Chinese hierarchical approach to the cardinal directions helps to account for the importance given to the east (right) side of the composition. The long valley of Mina, the Mosque of Ali (the fourth Caliph), and Uhud with the Mosque of Hamza are depicted in this propitious direction, which is associated with the renewal of life. Like the rising sun of the East, those who die a martyred death in Islam are reborn in Paradise on the Day of Judgement. The left column, to the West, the quadrant associated with the setting sun and autumn (hence death for the Chinese) includes Jabal Abu Qubbays. According to the principles of *fengshui*, it is appropriately placed at the northwest, and the holy cemetery at Mecca lies just below.

Although not organised in a strict horizontal grid, nor as symmetrical as the imperial city plan of Xian, the sites are nevertheless placed to give the map a similar balance and compositional harmony. Still, some sites that normally would be found in close proximity are placed far apart in the map. For example, in reality Muzdalifa is located halfway between Mina and Arafat, but on the panel it is placed opposite Mina and serves to balance the equally small Mosque of Khayf shown on the right. Mina, with its arcaded streets, which in reality lies between Mecca and Arafat, is placed at a right angle to Arafat. This matches the arcaded souk at Mu'da, opposite it on the left.

The artist's wish to call attention to the stations of the *hajj* may help to explain why Muzdalifa, Arafat, and Mina are not grouped together at the east and why Safa, at the foot of Jabal Abu Qubbays, is placed at the northwest. The corners of the Ka'ba, roughly face the four cardinal directions, while in the map and Fig. 3 they point to the northeast, northwest, southwest, and southeast. Thus, the northwest (upper left) corner of the Ka'ba faces Safa even though it is not in the east. Muzdalifa is placed at the southwest corner of the Ka'ba (lower left), the Mosque of Khayf in the valley of Mina at the southeast corner (lower right), and the Namira Mosque in the plain of Arafat is turned toward the northeast corner (upper right). This arrangement visually accentuates the importance of these sites and strengthens the iconic character of the Ka'ba as the centre of the *hajj* and of Islamic belief.

The Map as Cosmogram

A square mandala on a silk tapestry of the Yuan period in China in the Metropolitan Museum of Art, New York¹⁹ (Fig. 7) provides a point of comparison for the panel. The mandala, with a Tibetan format and Chinese symbols, reflects Buddhist cosmological ideas. The sacred Mt. Meru is placed at the centre, completely surrounded by mountain ranges and mountainous continents in the cardinal directions. As embodiments of mysterious power, mountains figure prominently throughout the history of Chinese belief, and were sacred destinations for Daoist and Buddhist pilgrimage. In Chinese cosmography, Mt. Song replaces Mt. Meru as the centre of the universe, and in the map, the Ka'ba's Black Stone, also placed centrally, parallels Mt. Song. Although the Ka'ba houses a stone, this would not have seemed objectionable to the map's artist, since rocks often represent mountains in Chinese gardens and as scholars' rocks.²⁰ As the House of the Lord, the Ka'ba, is thought to be the *axis mundi*, the cosmic pillar, connecting heaven, earth, and the underworld - the exact significance of Mt. Song in Chinese cosmology.²¹

The cosmographic arrangement of the Dongdasi map becomes all the more apparent when it is contrasted with a Chinese depiction of the Ka'ba with pilgrimage sites illustrated in the magazine *Aramco World*,²² (Fig. 8). The composition of this painting is much more informal and less iconic than the Dongdasi map, with pilgrimage routes threaded in and around pavilion-like shrines bearing Chinese-style roofs. Mountains and hills are liberally scattered throughout. Mosques and pilgrimage sites are often grouped naturalistically, and are not formally placed around the Ka'ba, as in the map.

The detailed portrayal of many of the sacred mountains, hills and rocks on the panel emphasises their importance, and provides some of the strongest evidence that the Chinese artist organised the pilgrimage sites in the form of a Chinese cosmogram. Unlike the examples in pilgrimage guides cited above, which are usually two-dimensional, and coloured blue or mauve, the hills and mountains on the panel have a strong presence. Although the square format of the Yuan mandala (Fig. 6) is more formal and abstract, the same basic schema is recognisable in the pictorial map.

Borders

A stylised decorative border surrounds the map, bringing additional life and embellishment to the painting. At the base of the panel are five additional borders (Fig. 9) painted in a provincial late-18th to early-19th century Qing style, incorporating a mixture

Fig. 8. Detail of a Chinese depiction of Mecca and surrounding sites from *Aramco World* (July-August, 1985): 15.

of motifs from earlier periods.²³

At the bottom of the panel are three scalloped lobe-like feet as found on a plinth, or the base of a throne. This suggests that the artist may have envisioned the panel as a stele, or tablet, set on a three-tiered carved base, supporting the throne of God. Buddhist and Daoist propitious symbols and signs of prosperity are depicted on these tiers. By the high Qing period, these auspicious motifs were part of a popular decorative vocabulary, losing any specific religious meaning. The tier projecting above the base has a large green oval medallion with crossed white rhinoceros horns in the centre, a green artemisia leaf (originally a Daoist symbol of eternity) to the left, and a branch of red coral to the right, all signs of good fortune during the Qing. Above is a wavy cloud-patterned band painted in yellow and red. On the tier above it is a central white and green oval cartouche, and three propitious symbols - a book at the left, interlocking circular coins in the middle, and an inverted "v" shape at the right, depicting a chiming stone used in court ritual.

Superimposed on this third tier is a band of stylised red lotus leaves edged in gold, recalling the design of blue-and-white ceramics made for the Muslim market during the Yuan and Ming periods, which became popular again in the 18th century. The chrysanthemum scroll with fleshy leaves surrounding the map, probably derived from a lotus scroll, is also typical of the high Qing. Its

Fig. 9. Borders at the bottom of the map in the Dongdasi.

alternating red and dark grey-green floral heads have Kufic or pseudo-Kufic inscriptions, probably with blessings or honorific names of Allah. These are similar to those found on the wood ceiling of the large prayer hall in the Dongdasi.

Conclusion

It seems likely that the Dongdasi map was composed during the high Qing dynasty, a time when Xian was a provincial capital and Muslims in northwestern China - as well as the country as a whole - were suffering economic problems, social discrimination, and a militarization of society. A Central Asian mystical and militant school of Sufism, the "New Teachings", fell on fertile ground and gained wide acceptance in areas of Gansu and southern Shaanxi province, including Xian. After a series of Muslim uprisings in 1781-83, the "New Teachings" with its messianic message of Islamic revivalism was banned and resulted only in deepening local antagonism. This was followed by a volatile period of harassment and rioting with the formation of Muslim militias to defend their homes. Mosques played an increasingly important political role in coalescing diverse Muslim factions. Things came to a head by the middle of the next century - in 1862, and for the next six years - when government troops were sent to Xian to crush a full-scale and bloody rebellion inspired by the Muslim secessionist movement in Gansu province. The two sides fought a bloody battle in the open fields of Xian but, reportedly, the imperial forces did not damage any of its mosques or its artefacts when fighting to take control.²⁴ During this tumultuous period, the Dongdasi would have again provided a safe haven for its congregation and enhanced their feeling of solidarity. The congregation may have felt reassured by this idealised and cosmological view of Islam.

The panel demonstrates how easily its artist accommodated traditional Buddhist and Daoist ideas of cosmology to an Islamic purpose. The faithful rendering of the pilgrimage sites provided a complete guide for students learning about the *hajj* and other Holy Sites. Their depiction is sufficiently realistic to make them easily identifiable, yet also abstract and schematic to add symbolic meaning.

The placement of the Ka'ba at the centre of the painting emphasises its importance as the focal point for Muslims. The geometric shape of the Ka'ba, which means "the cube" is well-suited for placement in a mandala, which often depicts geographic features - especially mountains - in highly schematic terms. The Chinese artist could easily transfer the familiar icon of the Ka'ba into the corresponding position of the mountain at the centre of a traditional Chinese cosmogram.

Further evidence of Chinese cosmological ideas can be found in the innovative organisation of the 22 sites. Safa, with Marwa nearby, is situated with the three important stations of the *hajj* - Jabal al-Rahman at Arafat, Mina, and Muzdalifa - at the four corners of the Ka'ba, instead of grouping them at the east in a geographically accurate manner. This arrangement emphasises their symbolic and ritual importance and echoes the symmetry of a cosmogram.

The alignment of the Holy Mosque at Mecca on the central axis, protected at the north by the wide Jabal al-Rahman at Arafat, and the Prophet's Mosque at Medina to the south, parallels the idealised organisation of Chinese imperial capitals. The composition is not geographically realistic, but instead seems to be based on the tenets of *fengshui*. This may explain the positioning of the verdant mountains, Jabal Nur and Jabal Thawr, to the south of the Ka'ba, and can be seen in the two flanking columns that help to give the map its grid-like configuration. The Holy Sites in these columns appear

to correspond to the geomantic significance of the cardinal directions. For example, the Chinese artist has placed various tombs in the west, the location traditionally associated with autumn and death.

The careful attention given to sacred mountains, enlarged in size, and placed in dominating positions, also calls to mind Chinese Buddhist and Daoist pilgrimage painting. Their depiction in the panel surrounding the Ka'ba infuses the landscape of the pilgrimage sites with special meaning. This idiosyncratic map, with its symbolic topography and explicit compositional arrangement functions on several levels. First, it is a reminder of the holy places, especially for a *hajji*. Second, it serves a didactic purpose, and third, it functions as a unique cosmogram for guiding a diverse congregation toward a transcendent experience of Islam.

This religious and cosmological synthesis of two diverse religious traditions brought together on the terminus of the ancient Asian trade routes results in a highly unusual work of art.²⁵ The representation of Islamic Holy Sites, infused with Buddhist cosmology and *fengshui* principles, found special appeal in the heterogeneous congregate of the Dongdasi.

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NOTES

1. See A.J. Wensinck, "Hadjdj: II The Origin of the Islamic Hadjdj and III The Islamic Hadjdj", *Encyclopaedia of Islam*, n.e., vol. III, 33-36; Ali S. Asani and Carney E. S. Gavit, "Through the Lens of Mirza of Delhi: The Debbas Album of Early-Twentieth-Century Photographs of Pilgrimage Sites in Mecca and Medina", *Muqarnas*, vol. 15 (1998), 179-99; F. E. Peters, *The Hajj* (Princeton, 1994); and Eldon Rutter, *The Holy Cities of Arabia* (London and New York, 1930), 179-99.
2. Most of the actual sites have changed over the years and, in some cases, radically. The Holy mosque of Mecca, for example has been enlarged greatly, and equipped with such modern conveniences as escalators, air-conditioning, and an underground parking facility. Many of the other sites depicted, especially those connected with tombs, were destroyed in the 19th century by the puritanical Wahhabi sect.
3. See Jill S. Cowen, "Dongdasi of Xian: A Mosque Built in the Guise of a Buddhist Temple", *Oriental Art*, vol. XXIX, no.2 (Summer 1983), 132 and 134-47.
4. The wood panel before being painted was probably prepared in the following way. After the wood was sanded down and resin added as a sealant, a thin layer of kaolin was used as a preparatory ground colour. I thank Spencer Throckmorton for this suggestion.
5. These approximate measurements and the location of the panel were confirmed by my friend Carol Mack who recently visited the Dongdasi.
6. The Edward Binney 3rd *Anthology* is numbered 1985.265. For publication see Edwin Binney 3rd and Walter B. Denny, *Turkish Treasures from the Collection of Edwin Binney 3rd* (Portland, Oregon, 1979), no. 100.154. Its 17th-century illustrations are found in the first of the six miscellaneous texts on pilgrimage sites and practices that comprise the *Anthology*. The first text, in Persian verse, is still unidentified but is thought to be similar to the *Futuh al-Haramayn*. I appreciate discussing this material with Andrea Riedlmayer, Bibliographer for the Aga Khan Program of Islamic Art and Architecture at Harvard University.
7. Norah Tittle, *Miniatures from Persian Manuscripts* (London, 1977), no. 254, 118. Its Persian text written by Muhyi Lari, who came from the island of Lar, in the Persian Gulf is dedicated to his patron Sultan Muzaffar ibn Mahmud Shah of Gujarat in 911/1505-06. See Barbara Schmitz, *Islamic Manuscripts in the New York Public Library* (New York 1992), 42 and fn. 2. I thank Sussan Babaie for reading difficult passages of this text.
8. See Schmitz, *Islamic Manuscripts*, 42-44 for discussion of the rotulus tradition.
9. Kurt Erdmann, "Qa'ba Tiles", *Ars Orientalis* III (1959), 192-97.
10. See Esin Atil, *The Age of Sultan Suleyman the Magnificent* (Washington and New York, 1987), fig. 22 and 63-65.
11. Rochelle Kessler, slide librarian in the Arthur M. Sackler Museum of Harvard University Art Museums graciously provided these correct measurements and folio numbers. The binding of the *Anthology* is only slightly larger than the folio size and measures 23 x 15cm.
12. For further description, meaning and changes through history see the *Encyclopaedia of Islam* entries for "Makka" and the other holy sites discussed in this article.
13. For a similar depiction in a Western, French 18th-century engraving see Walter B. Denny, "Paradise and the Word", *Images of Paradise in Islamic Art*, eds. Sheila S. Blair and Jonathan M. Bloom (Hanover, N.H., 1991), fig. 10a, 76.
14. See especially, Surah LVI: 28.
15. Richard F. Burton, *A Personal Narrative of a Pilgrimage to al-Madina & Meccah* (New York, 1964, reprint 1985), 159.
16. El-Basha, "Ottoman Pictures of the Mosque of the Prophet in Medina as Historical and Documentary Sources", *Islamic Art* III (1988-89), 227-43 provides the dates for these historical details. The Prophet's Mosque at Medina in Or. 343 fol. 374 has a different arrangement of minarets.
17. See Nancy Shatzman Steinhardt, *Chinese Imperial City Planning* (Hawaii, 1990), 10-18 for an excellent discussion of Chinese geomancy and the various components of an imperial city.
18. For discussion and plan of the city Sui Daxing-Tang Chang'an, see Steinhardt, 101-8 and fig. II, 1.
19. 1989.140, published in James C. Y. Watt and Anne E. Wardwell, *When Silk Was Gold* (New York, 1997), fig. 26, 101-3. Stephen McGuinness led me to this comparison and I appreciate his help. Ulku Bates also recognised that the layout of the sites on the pictorial panel may have been influenced by the pattern of a mandala.
20. John Hay, *Kernels of Energy, Bones of Earth: The Rock in Chinese Art* (New York, 1985); Robert Mowry et al, *Worlds Within Worlds: the Richard Rosenblum Collection of Chinese Scholar's Rocks* (Cambridge, 1997); and symposium papers on "The Rock in Chinese Art", Harvard University Art Museums, *Oriental Art* (1997).
21. See Kiyohiko Munakata, *Sacred Mountains in Chinese Art* (exhibition catalog: Krannert Art Museum and The Metropolitan Museum of Art) (Urbana-Champaign, Illinois, 1991). Frances Yuan called my attention to the fascinating article on Buddhist iconography of Dorothy C. Wong, "A Reassessment of the Representation of Mt. Wutai from Dunhuang Cave 61", *Archives of Asian Art* XLVI (1993), 27-52.
22. It is illustrated in Paul Lunde, "Muslims in China: The History", *Aramco World Magazine*, vol. 36, no. 4 (July-August, 1985): 15.
23. I am grateful to John Vollmer for his invaluable assistance in the dating and sources of these borders.
24. See Lanny Fields, *Tso Tsung-T'ang* (New York, 1976), 206-8; Jonathan Lipman, *Familiar Strangers* (Seattle and London, 1997), 118-19 and 123-24; and Raphael Israeli, *Muslims in China: A Study in Cultural Confrontation* (London and Atlantic Highlands, 1987), for interesting details. Morris Rossabi has been most helpful and generous in providing interpretation, sources and many of the specifics.
25. A similar synthesis of ideas can be found in the layout of the mosque, the decoration of the *qibla* and the addition of two hills in front of the *mibrab* in the scroll painting. See Cowen, "Dongdasi", 134-37 and Fig. 2 in this article.

EXHIBITION REVIEW

Shinto - the Sacred Art of Ancient Japan until 2nd December, 2001 The British Museum, London

Of all the events in Great Britain facilitated through the generosity of the Japan 2001 organisation, this is the one that takes us deepest into the understanding of that facet of their culture which has, over the millennia, mattered most to Japanese people. It makes us think about objects, practices and ideas that continue to play a major part in their lives as well as presenting a superb selection of star pieces from temples as well as from museums.

The exhibition, although presented as a single entity, is shown in two rooms (91 and 94) on two floors, though connected directly by a staircase.

The works are shown with plenty of space around them, facilitating contemplation: the off-white fabric backgrounds helped this, but one wondered why bright scarlet had been chosen for the bases of the vitrines. The labels are comprehensive and some inspired photographs set the scene, but the main interpretative medium is the excellent catalogue. Such restrained elegance is consonant with the theme.

The lower room houses a magnificent array of pre- and proto-historic pottery and metalwork going back to the Kofun period (3rd to 6th centuries CE), the upper room a no less impressive selection of sculpture, paintings and decorative arts from the succeeding Asuka period to the present day.

Linking the rooms is a concept of Shinto, that which pertains to *kami*. Generally translated as gods or spirits, *kami* were defined in the dictionary of Norinaga Motoori (1730 - 1801) as "anything whatsoever that is outside the ordinary, that possesses superior power or that is awe-inspiring".

Today, our understanding of Shinto is inevitably coloured by the Edict of 28th March 1868, separating Shinto from Buddhist institutions, establishing a network of Shinto shrines and reinforcing the cult of the Emperor as a descendant of the sun goddess Amaterasu. The exhibition makes it clear how different the position was from the introduction of Buddhism in 552 CE to 1868: we see a range of Shinto mandalas, an abundance of objects bearing Sanskrit characters, and temple guardians and lion dogs sculpted in the same techniques, with the same artistry, even signed by the same sculptors, as for Buddhist patrons.

Earthenware vessel with "flame" decoration. Middle Jomon period, 2500 - 1500 BCE. Ht: 46.5 cm. Tokamachi City Museum, Shinto - the Sacred Art of Japan, British Museum, London.

Figurine with clasped hands. Clay. Late Jomon period, 1500- 1000 BCE. Ht: 19.8 cm. Hachinoe City Museum. Shinto - the Sacred Art of Japan, British Museum, London.

Heavenly Being of the South. Wood. Kamakura Period, 1185 - 1333 (signed Shusei, 1322). Ht: 92.4 cm. Oyamazumi Jinja shrine. Shinto - the Sacred Art of Japan, British Museum, London.

Lion dog. Wood. Heian Period, 794 - 1185, Ht: 83 cm. Kibitsu Jinja shrine. Shinto - the Sacred Art of Japan, British Museum, London.

The inclusion of some superb ash-glazed stoneware vessels is based on the argument that craft tradition, fidelity to materials and to their own behaviour, and recognition of the limitations of the craftsman are all part of the Shinto attitude to art.

The exhibition concentrates on early, and therefore on upper-class manifestations of the religion: Edo period material and representations of popular cult like the Seven Gods are omitted.

Whether the magnificent "flame decoration" pots and figu-